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Figure 1-2: A: A β immunolabeling (Dako antibody) reveals a cored plaque with a dense focal center (arrowhead), surrounded by a halo and a diffuse corona of lightly labeled A β . B: A flame-shaped neurofibrillary tangle (arrow) labeled with AT8 antibody, with tau also accumulating in the dendritic shaft (arrowheads). Extracellular ghost tangles (small arrows) are also visible. Adapted from Duyckaerts et al. (2009)[2].

Figure 1-3: Representation of APP processing pathways. (A) The A β peptide sequence spans part of the ectodomain and the transmembrane region (red). (B) In the non-amyloidogenic pathway, APP is cleaved by α -secretase, followed by γ -secretase, preventing A β formation. (C) In the amyloidogenic pathway, APP is first cleaved by BACE1 (β -secretase), then by γ -secretase, generating A β peptides. Both pathways produce soluble ectodomains (sAPP α or sAPP β) and a shared intracellular domain (AICD). Adapted from O'Brien and Wong (2011)[3]. D: The γ -secretase complex sequentially cleaves the APP in two pathways generating A β peptides of various length. Adapted from Potier et al. (2024)[4].

Figure 1-4: Hypothesis of the origin of A β peptides in CAA. A β peptides could be (1) produced locally by cells from the NVU, (2) imported from the parenchyma for clearance, or (3) coming from the periphery, produced in other organs.

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Figure 1-7: A: Structure of brain vasculature and mural cell distribution. Pial arterioles branch from surface arteries and penetrate the brain parenchyma, transitioning into capillaries and eventually venules. Mural cells include vascular smooth muscle cells (SMCs), found in larger vessels, and pericytes, found in capillaries and post-capillary venules. Pericytes vary by location and are classified into subtypes such as ensheathing, transitional,

capillary, and post-capillary pericytes. Adapted from Uemura et al.(2020)[6] **B:** Structural organization and cellular composition of arteries, capillaries, and veins.

Figure 1-8: Tight and adherens junctions in brain endothelial cells. The figure illustrates key components of the blood-brain barrier, highlighting the organization of tight junctions and adherens junctions. Adapted from Kadry et al. (2020)[7].

Figure 1-9: Overview of the reprogramming of somatic blood cells into induced pluripotent stem cells (iPSCs) and their differentiation into organ-specific cell types. iPSCs, derived from patient blood samples, can generate all three germ layers (ectoderm, mesoderm, and endoderm) which give rise to various specialized cells, including neural, vascular, cardiac, hepatic, and pancreatic lineages. Abbreviations: iPSC, induced pluripotent stem cell; miRNA, microRNA. Reproduced from Adegunsoye et al. (2023)[8].

Figure 1-10: Comparative overview of CAA-related features across different conditions. The schematic summarizes key vascular pathologies in elderly control individuals (Ctrl), individuals with Down syndrome (DS), sporadic Alzheimer's disease (sAD), DS with Alzheimer's disease (DSAD), and APP microduplication (APPdup). **CAA frequency** progressively increases from Ctrl and DS to sAD, DSAD, and APPdup[9,1,10,5,11], with severity following a similar trend, from controls exhibiting milder CAA, to APPdup presenting severe CAA. **Frequencies of Intracerebral hemorrhage (ICH)**[12–15] and **microbleeds**[11,13,15,16] parallel CAA patterns. **Blood–brain barrier (BBB) integrity** is poorly characterized, but available data suggest a general decline in sAD relative to controls, with substantial interindividual variability likely influenced by age, genetic background and other factors[17] and very limited information on DS individuals [18]. Adapted from Valay and Potier (2025)[19]

Figure 2-1: hiPSC-ECs lines selection and differentiation. **A:** Site of the microduplication carried by the APPdup patient. The microduplication includes the genes GABPA, ATP5J, JAM2 and APP. **B:** Location of the CRISPR/Cas9 mediated deletion introduced in one of the three APP copies of the APPdup hiPSCs to generate an isogenic hiPSC control line. **C:** Names of the five cell lines with associated pathologies, expected CAA, and number of active APP copies. **D:** Summary of the differentiation protocol based on a previously published method from Patsch et al. (2015)[20].

Figure 2-2: Validation of the iPSC-ECs by immunostaining. **A:** The iPSC-ECs express tight junction ZO1 and adherens junction VE-cadherin. **B:** If not supplemented with additional VEGF165, the ECs appear more cobblestone shaped but lose their identity and die.

Figure 2-3: hiPSC-EC exhibit gene expression profiles similar to those of brain ECs. **A:** Table showing the number of expressed genes shared between hiPSC-ECs and transcriptomic signatures of various human brain vascular cell types, as defined by snRNA-seq from Sun et al. (2023)[21] showing more than 95% similarities between brain endothelial cells and hiPSC-ECs gene expression. Values in parentheses indicate the total number of genes in each reference signature (column headers) and the number of shared genes (table entries). **B:**

Cumulative variance explained by principal components in single-nuclei RNA-seq data. The 0.8 threshold is crossed at PC15. **C:**UMAP projection of bulk hiPSC-EC RNA-seq data onto a reference single-nuclei vascular cell atlas using Seurat. hiPSC-EC samples are shown in red and superpose with brain endothelial cells.

Figure 2-4: **A:** Relative higher $A\beta_{40}$ levels compared to the respective isogenic control in DSI (left) and APPdup (right). **B:** Relative higher $A\beta_{42}$ levels compared to the respective isogenic control in DSI (left) and APPdup (right). **C:** $\beta_{42}/A\beta_{40}$ ratio measured by MSD assay for each peptide alighting and significant increase in DSI compared to DSI isogenic whereas there is a more modest tendency to its decrease in APPdup compared to APPdup isogenic. Unpaired *t*-tests were performed between each condition and its respective isogenic control for all the sections. Statistical significance: * $p \leq 0.05$, *** $p \leq 0.001$, **** $p \leq 0.0001$.

Figure 2-5: $A\beta$ species identification by mass spectrometry. **A:** $A\beta$ peptides were immunoprecipitated using 6E10- and 4G8-conjugated magnetic beads and analyzed by LC/MS. **B:** Different $A\beta$ peptides detected in hiPSC-EC supernatants by mass spectrometry. Both bar height and color scale indicate signal intensity for each peptide. **C:** Total abundance (sum) of all $A\beta$ peptides identified in G confirming the MSD results. Numbers above bars indicate the number of distinct $A\beta$ peptides detected per group.

Figure 3-1: Principal component analysis of DSI, APPdup and their respective controls. **A:** PCA of DSI and its isogenic control, corrected for batch effects, reveals clear segregation by genotype and differentiation. **B:** PCA of APPdup and its isogenic control, corrected for passage number, reveals segregation by genotype and differentiation.

Figure 3-2: Results of the DGE performed on DSI vs DSI isogenic with a batch covariate. **A:** Bar plot showing the number of significantly dysregulated genes in the DSI hiPSC-ECs. **B:** Volcano plot showing massive dysregulations. **C:** MA plot showing no abnormal global trends. **D:** Heatmap associated with DSI DGE analysis.

Figure 3-3: Results of the DGE performed on APPdup vs APPdup isogenic with a passage covariate. **A:** Bar plot showing the number of significantly dysregulated genes in the APPdup hiPSC-ECs. **B:** Volcano plot showing more modest dysregulations compared to DSI. **C:** MA plot showing no abnormal global trends. **D:** Heatmap associated with APPdup DGE analysis.

Figure 3-4: Chromosome 21 Gene expression changes in hiPSC-ECs from individual with DS and patient carrying APPdup. **A:** Histogram showing the number of differentially expressed genes (y-axis) on chromosome 21 across fold change intervals (x-axis, bin width = 0.5) from the differential gene expression analysis on DSI and APPdup and their respective isogenic controls and confirming the trisomy in DSI with a high spike at FC 1.5. **B:** Intersection between Chr21 coding genes expressed in DSI (up) and APPdup (down) and the differentially expressed genes from their respective DGE analysis. **C:** Intersection between Chr21 coding genes dysregulated in DSI and APPdup respective DGE analysis showing

similarities but also distinct expressions changes. The list of the 64 Chr21 genes upregulated in DS1 only can be found in Supplementary Table 4.

Figure 3-5: Gene Set Enrichment Analysis (GSEA) reveals distinct pathway alteration in DS and APPdup hiPSC-ECs. **A, B:** Heatmap generated from the GSEA for the GOBP gene set "protein targeting to the membrane." Showing global down regulation of genes in both DS1 (**A**) and APPdup (**B**). **C, D:** Heatmap generated from the GSEA for the GOBP gene set "Maintenance of blood-brain barrier" Showing global up regulation of genes in DS1 (**C**) but not in APPdup (**D**).

Figure 3-6: The scale independence plot shows that a scale-free topology fit ($R^2 > 0.8$) is achieved at soft-thresholding power $\beta = 15$ in both the DS data set (**A**) and the APPdup dataset (**B**).

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Figure 3-9: Transcriptomic profiling of APPdup2 reveals high inter differentiation variability. **A:** PCA after correction for batch and passage shows no clear segregation between APPdup2 and isogenic samples. **B:** Volcano plot of DGE results using batch and passage as covariates reveals asymmetric dysregulation, with a bias toward upregulated genes and generally lower FDR compared to the first APPdup line. **C:** Bar plot showing the number of significantly dysregulated genes in the APPdup2 hiPSC-ECs. **D:** MA plot highlights an abnormal trend, with many genes exhibiting high fold changes but non-significant FDRs, suggesting possible sample heterogeneity. **E:** Heatmap of the differentially expressed genes shows poor segregation by genotype and greater variability across differentiations. Notably, the APPdup Diff2 sample clusters with isogenic controls, and one isogenic sample (diff3-1) appears as a strong outlier.

Figure 3-10: Transcriptomic profiling of APPdup2 improves by removing outliers. **A:** PCA after correction for batch and passage without outliers shows better segregation between APPdup2 and isogenic samples. **B:** Volcano plot of DGE results without outliers reveals symmetric dysregulations and improved FDR. **C:** Bar plot showing the number of significantly dysregulated genes in the APPdup2 hiPSC-ECs. **D:** MA plot without outliers shows less abnormal trend, but with still many genes exhibiting high fold changes but non-significant FDRs. **E:** Heatmap of the differentially expressed genes shows perfect segregation but variability across differentiations, especially in APPdup2.

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Figure 4-1: Immunostaining of endothelial markers and APP/A β in hiPSC-ECs. Immunofluorescence staining of (from top to bottom) adherens junction marker CD31, tight junction proteins Claudin-5 and Occludin, endothelial markers VWF and KDR, and APP/A β (6E10 antibody), with nuclei counterstained using DAPI, in hiPSC-ECs from individuals with DS, APPdup, their respective isogenic controls, and the independent control line WTS60. Scale bars: 50 μ m.

Figure 4-2: Quantification of immunostaining for endothelial markers and APP/A β in hiPSC-ECs. **A:** Relative cell area in each hiPSC-EC line. **B-I:** Quantification of adherens junctions VE-cadherin (**B**) and CD31 (**C**), tight junctions Claudin-5 (**D**), Occludin (**E**) and ZO1 (**F**), endothelial markers VWF (**G**) and KDR (**H**) and APP/A β (6E10, **I**). All measurements represent relative signal per cell, normalized to the respective isogenic control line, including cell area (**A**). Statistical analysis was performed using one-way ANOVA for each comparison. Statistical significance: * $p \leq 0.05$, ** $p \leq 0.01$, *** $p \leq 0.001$, **** $p \leq 0.0001$.

Figure 4-3: Visualization of endothelial monolayers on Transwell membranes. Representative immunofluorescence images showing homogenous endothelial monolayers derived from different hi-PSC-EC lines cultured on Transwell inserts coated with fibronectin. Cells were stained for VE-cadherin (green), CD31 (red), and nuclei (DAPI, blue). All cell lines formed continuous monolayers exhibiting well-defined adherens junctions. Color variations between images are due to differences in acquisition settings; however, all cell lines formed continuous monolayers with well-defined adherens junctions.

Figure 4-4: Measure of permeability of monolayers of hiPSC-ECs from DS and APPdup. **A:** Schematic of the experimental setup used to measure permeability: a 70KDa FITC-dextran passage through a hiPSC-EC monolayer cultured on Transwell inserts was monitored over time, and permeability was calculated using the formula adapted from Czupalla et al. (2014)[22]. **B, C:** Time-course of FITC fluorescence accumulation in the lower well compartment, showing reduced tracer passage in the presence of hiPSC-EC monolayers from DS1 (**B**) and APPdup (**C**) compared to cell-free controls. **D, E:** Permeability values over time for DS1-associated (**D**) and APPdup-associated (**E**) hiPSC-EC, including controls. Thrombin treatment was used as a positive control to disrupt adherens junctions and increase permeability. **F:** Normalized permeability at 120 minutes in DS1, its isogenic control, and the independent control WTS60, showing a significantly reduced permeability in DS1 compared to both controls. **G:** Normalized permeability at 120 minutes in APPdup, its isogenic control, and WTS60, showing a significantly increased permeability in APPdup relative to both

controls. Statistical analysis was performed using one-way ANOVA with multiple comparisons. Statistical significance: * $p \leq 0.05$, ** $p \leq 0.01$, **** $p \leq 0.0001$.

Figure 5-1: hi-PSC-ECs form a confluent monolayer on artificial basement membrane in both APPdup (A) and isogenic control lines (B). Immunostaining for VE-cadherin (green) and CD31 (red) confirms the presence of endothelial junctions and appropriate cell–cell contact.

Figure 5-2: Formation of cerebrovascular organoids to investigate the role of the vasculature in the formation of A β deposits. A: formation of autologous and heterologous organoids B: Protocol of the formation of fusion organoids.

Figure 5-3: Preliminary characterization of cerebrovascular organoids. A: Spontaneous fusion of dorsal forebrain (blue arrowhead) and vascular (red arrowhead) organoids observed within a few days of co-culture (no differences observed between genotypes). B: Immunostaining of 90-day-old dorsal forebrain organoids derived from APPdup iPSCs (left) and isogenic controls (right), showing Caspase-3 (green), A β (6E10, red), and Sox2 (white) expression. C: Quantification of immunostaining signals across dorsal forebrain organoids at different developmental stages. Signals are normalized to DAPI (to adjust for organoid size and acquisition variability) and to the isogenic control.

List of Supplementary Figures

Supplementary Figure 1: Workflow of record selection used to write the introduction and identify the research gap regarding the BBB in DS in the context of CAA.

Supplementary Figure 2: Weighted gene co-expression network analysis (WGCNA) in DS1, its isogenic control, and independent controls after module merging. A: Gene dendrogram generated by hierarchical clustering based on topological overlap, prior to module merging. The red horizontal line indicates the module merging threshold (cut height = 0.25), below which modules were merged based on similarity in eigengene expression profiles. B: Heatmap of eigengene adjacency showing correlations between merged modules. Warmer colors indicate higher correlation between module eigengenes, suggesting co-expression similarity. C: Merged module–trait relationship heatmap. Cells show Pearson correlations (with p-values) between module eigengenes and DS traits; color indicates correlation strength and direction. D to H: Scatter plots showing the relationship between gene significance (GS) for the trait and module membership (MM) in selected merged module with an absolute module–trait correlation > 0.5 and exhibiting genes with a significant positive correlation ($r > 0.4$, $p < 0.05$) between GS and MM, indicating key genes associated with both the trait and the module.

Supplementary Figure 3: WGCNA in APPdup and its isogenic control after module merging. A: Gene dendrogram generated by hierarchical clustering based on topological overlap, prior to module merging. The red horizontal line indicates the module merging threshold (cut height = 0.25), below which modules were merged based on similarity in eigengene expression profiles. B: Heatmap of eigengene adjacency showing correlations between merged modules. Warmer colors indicate higher correlation between module

eigengenes, suggesting co-expression similarity. C: Merged module–trait relationship heatmap. Cells show Pearson correlations (with p-values) between module eigengenes and APPdup traits; color indicates correlation strength and direction. D to G: Scatter plots showing the relationship between gene significance (GS) for the trait and module membership (MM) in selected merged module with an absolute module–trait correlation > 0.5 and exhibiting genes with a significant positive correlation ($r > 0.4$, $p < 0.05$) between GS and MM, indicating key genes associated with both the trait and the module.

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